

1

yok'enodzeedz

2

ggaaggoz

3

Naat'oh.

4

Nodenotl'ee.

5

telege

6

dotson'

2

bird

1

drone
**“bumblebee in
the sky”**

4

It has landed.

3

It is flying.

6

raven

5

eagle

7

ełts'eyh

8

kk'ok'enaalt'oghenh

9

Neentaanh.

10

Kk'onheedeneeyh.

11

Ggaaggoz neetaanhu

12

Naaghelmətl.

8

pilot

7

wind

10

They are working.

9

See it.

12

It is spinning.

11

Bird's eye view

13

ts' emaa

14

keɫdon'

15

k'eɫdon'

16

t'eghet

17

maats

18

**melaalzene/
dets'ene**

14

dandelion

13

spruce tree

16

**balsam poplar
(cottonwood) tree**

15

fireweed

18

Canada goose

17

seagull